

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.9 to AD4.1 – FAQ Sheet for Children

WP 4

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PARC TASK 4.1 TEMPLATE

QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS

FOR CHILDREN PARTICIPANTS (6-11 YEARS)

*[title of study, e.g. **PARC aligned study on [specify name of pollutant(s)]***

INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO USE THIS TEMPLATE

This document is a template, which can be used to develop an assent form for children participants in PARC surveys, if demanded by the study design and national requirements. You may introduce changes, to meet those requirements. To use this template, adjust the text as you find appropriate for your study.

The PARC templates for children are:

"CH_IL – Information leaflet": Information Leaflet for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_QA – Questions and Answers": Questions and Answers for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_AF – Assent form": Assent form for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_FS – Fact Sheet": Fact sheet on chemicals for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"ADOL-CH_CIC - Consent Form Parent or Legal Guardian": "Adjusted Consent Form for Parents / Legal Guardians of Young Participants".

[title of study, e.g. PARC biomonitoring study on [specify name of pollutant(s)]

Questions and Answers for young participants (6-11 years)

We are inviting you to take part in our research study called "PARC". Before you decide if you want to take part, please read this information *[adjust if necessary: together with your parents]* and ask us any questions you may have. We will be very happy to answer them!

Why is this study being done?

We want to learn about chemicals in the bodies of children who live in Europe and to think of find ways to lower these chemicals in our environment in order to keep us healthy.

Is the research safe and who has checked it?

An expert group of people, who do not belong to our team, have examined our study and decided that it is safe for you to take part if you want to. This independent group of people is called *[adjust if necessary: a Research Ethics Committee]*.

Why are you asking me?

You are invited because we wish to study children who are [XX to YY] years old and live in [ZZ name of sampling region]. [Describe any other appropriate inclusion criteria].

If you decide to take part, you will be one of [specify number: ...] children in [specify your country: ...] and a total of [specify number: ...] children in [specify total number of participating countries: ...] European countries, who will participate in our study!

Do I have to say “yes”?

No, not at all! It's completely up to you! If you don't want to, just say so and nobody will mind! If you decide to take part and later change your mind, that's OK as well! Just let us or your parents know.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you are able, you will write your name on a form that says you understand the study and that you agree to take part. You get to keep a copy of this form, together with this leaflet. Your [parents / mom / dad/ guardian] will tell us when it's a good time for you to meet with our research team. [You will visit our research team at XXXX / be visited by our research team at your home / school]. We will ask you to give us a small amount of [pee / hair sample cut from the back of your head in a way that doesn't show]. These are called “samples” and our scientists will examine them in their laboratories to find out how much of some chemicals are in them. We will also ask your [parents / mom / dad to answer some questions about where you live, what food you normally eat and describe other questions you may ask about the child].

We expect the visit to last around [XXX] minutes.

Our scientists will store small amounts of your samples in a 'BioBank'. This is a bit like a 'special bank', but instead of collecting money, we collect samples from our bodies and keep them safe to use in future studies similar to this one.

The information that your parents will provide about you will also be kept in a special computerized bank called a 'DataBase', for use in future similar studies.

Will the study upset me or help me?

We will do everything we can to avoid upsetting you in any way. *[You may feel a little discomfort when you give a sample. Explain any other possible inconvenience.]* If you are upset about anything at any time, please let us know immediately.

How will the study help people?

We hope that our study will help boys and girls like you all over Europe to keep healthy.

We will do so by informing the government, scientists and politicians in **[your country]** and all of Europe about what we learn from our study and about new ways we think can protect us from dangerous chemicals in our environment.

You will feel proud of yourself for helping create a healthier environment for all the children in your country and across Europe!

Describe if a gift is given as an incentive: We would like to thank you for taking part and adding value to our study by offering you ...]

What happens if I change my mind about taking part?

After you let us know, we will destroy any samples that are left in our BioBank and all the information about you from our DataBase. Samples and information already used for research will not have any information that can identify you.

What shall I do now?

Now that you know about the study, just think about if you agree to take part.

Who can I ask about this?

Your [mum / dad / parents] have been given lots of information. You can also speak to our scientists, who will be happy to answer your questions. Just give us a call at the number [phone number of contact person] and ask to talk to [name of contact person]. You can also ask us questions when we meet with you to take your samples or at any time in the future!

Want to know more?

Visit our website to find out more! www.eu-parc.eu

This template was adapted from the HBM4EU document available at www.hbm4eu.eu